

STRUCTURAL DESIGN AND STRENGTH ANALYSIS OF THE TANK-CONTAINER WITH COMPOSITE TANK FOR MULTIMODAL TRANSPORTATIONS OF CHEMICALLY AGGRESSIVE FLUIDS AND PETROCHEMICAL PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

A complete cycle of design, manufacturing and finite element strength analysis of the tank-container with fiberglass composite tank for multimodal transportation of chemically aggressive fluids and petrochemical products is presented. The tank-container has been designed for road, rail and offshore deep-water transportations that places high demands on the structure in accordance with RID/ADR and IMDG requirements. The tank itself was manufactured by use of the both filament winding and vacuum infusion technologies. 3D finite element model was developed for representation of actual layups and geometry of the wound and infused composite layers of the tank. That model analysed all normative load cases. Besides the normative load cases the FE simulation of the dynamic crash test was carried out by coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian analyses. As a result of such dynamic simulation the threshold SRS curves were obtained to guarantee the requested minimum 4g longitudinal acceleration at low front fittings of the container frame. For the first step of validation of the developed FE model, the calculated results were compared with results of the hydraulic test of the tank. Some idea of subcomponent tests is proposed as well for analysis of the critical zones of the structure and verification of the FE models.

1 INTRODUCTION

The need for development of tank-container fleet for multimodal transportation chemical and petrochemical products caused significant role of dangerous chemical cargo in the modern transport streams. In the world according to International Tank Container Organization (ITCO) in 2014, it was 394,000 tank-containers in circulation with the growth of the fleet up to 12% in comparison with 2013. Frame elements and tanks of the fleet are almost 100% made of metal. The advantages of the tank-container with the composite tank are longer service life compared with metal counterparts, reducing operating costs and energy consumption in the production, improve of the safety of operation (including the extension of the service life). Furthermore, the list of dangerous chemical goods in a temperature range of operation of up to + 50°C -60°C can be extended to methanol, isopropanol, and the sulfuric acid concentration of from 75% to 80% using composite tank.

2 STRUCTURE, PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGIES AND MATERIALS

The tank-container has the following parameters.

Parameter	Value
Maximum gross weight, tons	36.00
Own weight with a container, tons	4.35
Volume capacity, m ³	24.00
Allowable working pressure, MPa	0.4
Testing pressure, MPa	0.6

Table 1: Principal parameters of the tank-container.

General view of the tank-container and a scheme of structural layers of the composite tank are shown at Figure 1. The tank has a connecting «skirt» bolted to steel mandrels of the frames of the container. Materials of the tank are polymeric fiberglass composites obtained by vacuum infusion and filament winding. The structural layers of the barrel and the «skirt» are manufactured by filament winding above the primarily infused end caps. Such technology forms a monolithic material including material interfaces inside of the tank structure. The infused end caps and the wound «skirt» have quasi-isotropic layups. The tank barrel is wound by unidirectional plies in order to provide stiffness distribution as 2/1 in circumferential and longitudinal direction respectively. Material properties of the infused and wound layers obtained from standard ASTM tests are given in Table 2.

Figure 1: General view of the tank-container and a scheme of structural layers of the composite tank

Properties		Infused quasi-isotropic layers	Wound unidirectional layers
E_1	[GPa]	20.9	42.9
E_2	[GPa]	20.9	12.3
ν_{12}	–	0.28	0.27
G_{12}	[GPa]	8.94	4.0
X_T	[MPa]	377	987
Y_T	[MPa]	377	12.1
X_C	[MPa]	268	474
Y_C	[MPa]	268	102
S	[MPa]	183	9.81

Table 2: Material properties of the infused quasi-isotropic and the wound unidirectional layers.

4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The FE models includes only structural layers, i.e. the strength properties of the inner chemically resistant and the flame-retardant coating layers are not taken into account. Mass fraction of these layers in the tank structure was applied as inertial loads. Analysis of areas of installation of flanges of access hatch, air, cargo and safety valves was performed using a local finite element models. ABAQUS software was used for modeling and analysis.

For modeling of the tank itself three-dimensional multi-layer finite shell elements SC8R with the characteristic size of 25 mm in regular zones and 1 mm in the areas of joints were used. The container frame and fittings were modeled by single-layer two-dimensional S4R. Mechanical contact was setup between the respective surfaces of the tank and the container frames. Rigid fasteners modeled the bolt joints of the tank to the container frame. Some details of the finite element model of the tank-container are explained at Figure 2. Calculation results are illustrated for 0.4 MPa and 0.6 MPa hydraulic pressure load cases below at Figure 3.

Figure 2: Finite element model of the tank-container with composite vessel

Figure 3: FEM strain distributions for 0.4 MPa (on the left) and 0.6 MPa (on the right) hydraulic pressure

For preliminary evaluation of strength of the manufactured tank, the hydraulic pressure test was carried out at ADMOR Composites testing laboratory (Valkeakoski, Finland) in accordance with RID/ADR requirements. Illustrative pictures about preparation of the test are given at Figure 4. The tank has been filled by water almost up to its volume capacity and then pressurized up to 0.4 MPa design pressure and, as next loading step, up to 0.6 MPa testing pressure. The obtained test results were applied to validation of the FE calculation model.

Circumferential and axial strains were measured as values averaged over the circle and the length of the tank. The measured section was taken at the middle between the edge of the connecting “skirt” and stiffener. The calculated strain distribution at this area are shown at Figure 3. The test results are given at Table 3 in comparison with FEM results.

Pressure, MPa	0.4	0.6
Circumferential strain, %, Test	0.093	0.160
Circumferential strain, %, FEM	0.103	0.170
Axial strain, %, Test	0.035	0.053
Axial strain, %, FEM	0.030	0.045

Table 3: Hydraulic pressure test and FEM results.

Figure 4: Preparation of hydraulic pressure testing of the tank at ADMOR Composites laboratory

One of the most critical point of the study is an analysis of the material interfaces inside of the tank structure. For calculation of safety factor of the material interfaces, Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) [1] was applied there. For expression of effective energy release rate the power law was applied

$$G_{eqiuv} = \left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}}\right)^\beta + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIC}}\right)^\gamma \geq 1, \quad (1)$$

The safety factor of the material interfaces by load of crack initiation is defined as:

$$K_{delam} = 1/\sqrt{G_{eqiuv}} \quad (2)$$

Critical energy release rates of the material interfaces and parameters of VCCT criteria obtained by ASTM D5528-01 (G_{IC}) and ASTM D6671-01 (G_{IIC}) tests are given at Table 4. Locations of some analysis area are shown at Figure 5. For one of the most critical load cases results of calculation of safety factors of crack initiation load are summarized at Table 5.

Critical energy release rate		Winding/Winding	Infusion/Infusion	Winding/Infusion
G_{IC}	[N/m]	1010	1350	312
G_{IIC}	[N/m]	5609	3293	2349
α	-	1	1	1
β	-	1	1	1
γ	-	1	1	1

Table 4: Critical energy release rates of the material interfaces and parameters of VCCT criteria.

Figure 5: Modeling of the material interfaces

Load case	Material interfaces and analysis are				
	1	2	3	4	5
	W/I	W/W	W/W	W/W	W/I
Longitudinal overload 4g	5.9	15.6	17.8	16.8	6.1
Hydraulic pressure 0.4MPa	7.1	18.1	19.5	18.8	8.3

Table 5: Safety factors for the material interfaces.

5 CRUSH TEST SIMILATION

One the most critical point of strength analysis and testing of the tank-containers is the crush test in accordance with requirements of the IMDG (International Maritime Dangerous Goods) Code. For analysis of stress/strain state of the composite tank due to its dynamic interaction with liquid during impact, it is necessary to simulate the crush test before it will be carried out as a full-scale test on real structure.

The scheme of the crush test is shown at Figure 6. The tank of the tested tank-container (1) is filled with water up to 97% of its capacity and then the tank-container is installed on a railway platform by rigidly fixing of the lower frame fittings for all degrees of freedom. The tank-container is installed as close as possible to the impacted edge of the platform. The gaps between the fittings and fixtures are minimized.

The impacting car (2) is accelerated from a hill, hitting the platform with the set tank-container, and then the system moves to a collision with a fixed car-head (3). For damping of the impact, every car has their own installed absorber by energy capacity of 130kJ. In the simulation the reference car-striker is modeled by a rigid contact surface connected with a mass of 84 tons in accordance with the test requirements [2].

The accelerometers are mounted on each of the two lower frame fittings and the signal from which is sampled at a minimum frequency of 1000 Hz [2]. The testing oscillograms includes recording the amplitude of the longitudinal acceleration during the impact. The impact speed is chosen from the requirement of providing a longitudinal acceleration of the lower fitting at least 4g, and moreover, based upon data SRS curve must lie above the threshold curve (see Figure 8), which is indicated in the test requirements given at [2].

Figure 6: A scheme of the impact test on the longitudinal acceleration of 4g

Modeling of the dynamic interaction of the tank with water during the impact is carried out in coupling Euler-Lagrange formulation, where the calculation of deformation of the structure is carried out on Lagrangian finite-element mesh and the calculation of the moving water on the Euler mesh. The FE model of the tank-container placed in the Euler volume is shown at Figure 7. The upper boundary of the initial volume of water is displayed by red line in the figure. The volume of water was simulated by three-dimensional finite elements of EC3D8R type.

Figure 7: A simulation of the 4g crush test by coupling Euler-Lagrange method

Mi-Grüneisen equation of state is applied for simulation of the dynamic displacements of water within the Euler mesh. The parameters of the equation are given in Table 6.

Parameter		Value
Density	[kg/m ³]	1000
Dynamic viscosity	[Pa×sec]	0.001
Sound speed	[m/s]	1450
Grüneisen's gamma	–	0

Table 6: Parameters of Mi-Grüneisen equation for water.

Because of the simulation, a scaled in amplitude and filtered signal from the lower corner fitting of the model was obtained (Figure 8, on the left). The acceleration oscillogram converted into SRS curve has no points on the graph below the threshold curve (Figure 8, on the right). Thus, the simulation has been reached the required level of the impact loading. Comparison of the calculated and experimental SRS curves provides a close match of the amplitude at low frequencies about 10 Hz. Moreover, a similar quality of the SRS – curves can be mentioned.

Figure 8: Oscillogram of the simulated acceleration-time signal at of the lower front fitting (on the left) and the threshold, simulated and testing SRS – curves (on the right).

As a result of the calculation, it was determined that the critical area with the largest maximum strains and stresses is located at the end cap area at the impact side, and extends along the border of the infused and wound components of the tank (Figure 9, on the left).

Note, that while for calculation of the SRS curve from the lower front fitting the simulated signal is longer than 1.2 sec., the peak of the strain at the end cap of the of the tank is achieved in less than 0.1 sec. after the impact interaction begins (Figure 9, on the right).

Figure 9: Max principal strain in the vessel (on the left) and calculated strain-time curve (on the right).

6 PROPOSAL FOR SUBCOMPONENT TESTING

Most reliable test is to manufacture a prototype according to the design and have it tested. However, 2D specimen is proposed to save cost for molds and material testing. It is important that the real situation is simulated well. Because of the circular shape of the joint displacements in circumferential and radial direction are restricted. It has to be accounted for a flat 2D sample. To prevent displacement perpendicular to the adhesive joint, testing of a double lap joint is the usual procedure. Therefore, the following test set-up is proposed here. Below at Figure 10, a scheme of compression test of the proposed subcomponent is shown.

Figure 10: The proposed subcomponent test for the critical area of the «skirt»-to-barrel joints.

7 CONCLUSIONS

A complete cycle of design, manufacturing and finite element strength analysis of tank-container with fiberglass composite tank for multimodal transportation of chemically aggressive fluids and petrochemical products is presented. 3D finite element model was developed for representation of actual layups and geometry of the wound and infused composite layers of the tank. FE simulation of the dynamic crash test was carried out by coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian analyses. As a result of such dynamic simulation the threshold SRS curves were obtained to guarantee the requested minimum 4g longitudinal acceleration at low front fittings of the container frame during the crush test. For the first step of validation of the developed FE model, the calculated results were compared with results of the hydraulic test of the tank.

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